

Assessing Macroeconomic Performance of OIC Member Countries Using Data Envelopment Analysis, DEA

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In this study, a mathematical programming based technique in productivity management, known as data envelopment analysis, DEA is used to estimate how well the nations of the *Organization of the Islamic Conference, OIC* utilize their resources. A high growth rate (as indicated by the change in gross domestic product), a low rate of inflation, a low rate of unemployment and a favorable trade balance are four main targets or objectives of a nation's macroeconomic policy makers. Based on selected macroeconomic input and output indicators, we apply three versions of an output-oriented DEA model under the assumption of variable returns to scale to assess the relative macroeconomic performance of 54 member countries for the year 2007. The three versions produced consistent results. Three fuel-exporting countries and four least-developed countries top the performance list with Iran and Yemen at the bottom. Of a subset of 33 fuel-exporting and medium-developed countries, nine (seven and two respectively) top the list. The results were analyzed to identify the possible merits of efficiency and sources of inefficiency.

1 Introduction

Managing an economy is no easy task. A high growth rate (as indicated by the change in gross domestic product, GDP), a low rate of inflation

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(as depicted by the change in consumer price index, CPI), a favorable trade balance and a high rate of employment are main targets or mission of a nation's macroeconomic policy maker. The sum of inflation rate and unemployment rate is associated with the undesirable Okun's *misery index* [11] which is literally a nightmare to policy makers and provides a pessimistic measure of the macroeconomic performance of a nation. Thus the performance of a nation needs to be assessed and evaluated periodically so that any shortcoming or underachievement can be identified, analyzed and appropriate steps taken to remedy it.

Many studies on macroeconomic and development performance of regions, cities and nations have been conducted and reported in the literature. Charnes, Cooper and Li [4] used DEA to evaluate the economic performance of 28 selected Chinese cities following the government's program of economic development. Sueyoshi [16] extended the study to measuring and evaluating the industrial performance which also explored the returns to scale of these cities. The macroeconomic performance of ten Asian economies with special attention to Taiwan was studied and summarized by Lovell [10] in terms of the four main output indicators. Despotis [7] extended the applicability of the DEA model with variable returns to scale to estimate the relative efficiency of countries in Asia and the Pacific in converting incomes to human development. Other regional studies utilizing DEA include [9], [12] and [13]. In most of these regional studies, the units under evaluation such as nations, cities and regions are nearly homogeneous in terms of their socio-economic background and geographical location.

This study seeks to assess the macroeconomic performance of 54 (out of the 57) selected member countries of the Organization of the Islamic Conference, OIC for the year 2007, by utilizing the output-oriented DEA model under the assumption of variable returns to scale, VRS. The complexity of OIC as the second largest inter-governmental organization after the United Nations motivates us to undertake this study. The 57 member countries are dispersed over a large geographical region spanning over four continents. As a group, the OIC countries account for one-sixth (or 16.67%) of the world's area, extending from Albania (Europe) in the North to Mozambique (Africa) in the South, and from Guyana (Latin America) in the West to Indonesia (Asia) in the East. Some of the member countries such as Benin, Burkina Faso, Djibouti, Gabon and Suriname (to name just a few) are less known (at

least to the authors), and this triggers us further interest to embark on this study. OIC community also exhibits high level of income divergence with huge gap between the rich and the poor countries. Based on 2007 statistics, the average GDP per capita for OIC as a group is US\$2595, ranging from a low US\$206 (for Guinea-Bissau) to a high US\$72849 (for Qatar) [15]. This reflects a difference of 354 times between the richest and the poorest. Thus a study of an organization with such high level of heterogeneity is likely to produce interesting (and probably contradicting) findings.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section provides a brief overview of the OIC member countries and their macroeconomic performance in comparison with the world, developing and developed countries. This is followed by the DEA methodology related to the three versions employed in the study – the extended multiplier form, the helmsman model of Lovell [10] and the *generic* input-output model of Ramanathan [14]. Section 4 focuses on the macroeconomic data utilized for the study while section 5 presents the results, interpretations and policy implications. The final section concludes with highlights for future research.

2 Overview of OIC

The OIC is an international inter-governmental organization with a permanent delegation to the United Nations. It was established on 25 September 1969, following the loss of Muslim holy sites in Jerusalem. According to its charter, the OIC aims to preserve Islamic social and economic values; promote solidarity amongst member states; increase cooperation in social, economic, cultural, scientific, and political areas; uphold international peace and security; and advance education, particularly in the fields of science and technology. Over the last forty years, the membership has grown from its founding members of 25 to 57 countries.

Table 1 lists the 57 member countries (which for reference purposes are denoted as DMU01, DMU02,..., DMU57) according to their economic attributes and regional locations. Of the fifteen fuel-exporting countries (OIC-FEC), ten are from Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. Twenty medium-developed countries (OIC-MDC) are scattered on the four continents while the remaining twenty-two are grouped under least-developed countries (OIC-LDC), of which seventeen belong to Sub-

Saharan Africa region with low income per capita. In terms of gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, only seven nations are categorized as high income group. Except for Brunei (from East Asia and Pacific), all countries in the high income group are OIC-FEC from MENA. The upper and lower-middle income group is dispersed over a larger region, while the majority of lower-income group is concentrated in the Sub-Saharan Africa region. In view of this non-homogeneity, results produced by any performance assessment on these groups should be handled with caution.

Table 1. OIC member countries according to categories and locations.

DMU	Country	Group ¹	Income ²	Region ³
DMU01	Afghanistan	LDC	Low	South Asia
DMU02	Albania	MDC	Lower-Middle	Europe & Central Asia
DMU03	Algeria	FEC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU04	Azerbaijan	FEC	Lower-Middle	Europe & Central Asia
DMU05	Bahrain	FEC	High	MENA
DMU06	Bangladesh	LDC	Low	South Asia
DMU07	Benin	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU08	Brunei	FEC	High	East Asia & Pacific
DMU09	Burkina Faso	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU10	Cameroon	MDC	Lower-Middle	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU11	Chad	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU12	Comoros	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU13	Cote d'Ivoire	MDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU14	Djibouti	LDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU15	Egypt	MDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU16	Gabon	FEC	Upper-Middle	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU17	Gambia	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU18	Guinea	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU19	Guinea-Bissau	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU20	Guyana	MDC	Lower-Middle	Latin A & Caribbean
DMU21	Indonesia	MDC	Lower-Middle	East Asia & Pacific
DMU22	Iran	FEC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU23	Iraq	FEC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU24	Jordan	MDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU25	Kazakhstan	MDC	Upper-Middle	Europe & Central Asia
DMU26	Kuwait	FEC	High	MENA
DMU27	Kyrgyzstan	MDC	Low	Europe & Central Asia
DMU28	Lebanon	MDC	Upper-Middle	MENA
DMU29	Libya	FEC	Upper-Middle	MENA
DMU30	Malaysia	MDC	Upper-Middle	East Asia & Pacific
DMU31	Maldives	LDC	Lower-Middle	South Asia
DMU32	Mali	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU33	Mauritania	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU34	Morocco	MDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU35	Mozambique	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU36	Niger	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU37	Nigeria	FEC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU38	Oman	FEC	High	MENA
DMU39	Pakistan	MDC	Low	South Asia
DMU40	Palestine	MDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU41	Qatar	FEC	High	MENA
DMU42	Saudi Arabia	FEC	High	MENA
DMU43	Senegal	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa
DMU44	Sierra Leone	LDC	Low	Sub-Saharan Africa

Table 1. (Continue)

DMU*	Country	Group¹	Income²	Region³
DMU45	Somalia	LDC	Low	Sub-Sahara Africa
DMU46	Sudan	LDC	Lower-Middle	Sub-Sahara Africa
DMU47	Suriname	MDC	Upper-Middle	Latin A & Caribbean
DMU48	Syria	MDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU49	Tajikistan	MDC	Low	Europe & Central Asia
DMU50	Togo	LDC	Low	Sub-Sahara Africa
DMU51	Tunisia	MDC	Lower-Middle	MENA
DMU52	Turkey	MDC	Upper-Middle	Europe & Central Asia
DMU53	Turkmenistan	FEC	Lower-Middle	Europe & Central Asia
DMU54	Uganda	LDC	Low	Sub-Sahara Africa
DMU55	United Arab	FEC	High	MENA
DMU56	Emirates	MDC	Low	Europe & Central Asia
DMU57	Uzbekistan	LDC	Low	MENA
	Yemen			

Notes:

- 1) FEC: Fuel-exporting country , LDC : Least-developed country MDC: Medium-developed country.
- 2) Low income (GDP per capita < US\$650) , Lower-middle income (GDP per capita US\$2000) ,Upper-middle income (GDP per capita < US\$9999), High income
- 3) (GDP per capita > US\$10000).
- 4) MENA : Middle East and North Africa countries.

* DMU refers to *decision making unit*.

Source: *Annual Economic Report on The OIC Countries*, 2008. Statistical, Economic and Social Research Training Centre for Islamic Countries (SESRIC).

Table 2 provides basic facts on selected economic indicators for OIC in comparison with the world, developed countries and developing countries for the year 2007. With a total population of 1422.8 million, OIC accounts for about 21.89% of the world population. This is equivalent to about a quarter of the total population of the developing countries but exceeds the total population of the developed countries by about 1.45 times. The largest contribution is Indonesia with 224.9 million while the least populated is the oil-rich Brunei with 0.4 million.

Table 2. Basic facts on OIC, the world, developed and developing countries, 2007.

Indicators	OIC	World	Developed countries	Developing countries
1. Population (millions)	1422.8	6500.5	983.9	5516.6
2. GDP (US\$, billions)	3692.6	54311.6	39131.1	15180.6
3. GDP per capita (US\$)	2595.0	8355.0	39772.0	2752.0
4. Export (US\$ billions)	1356.5	13812.8	7593.4	6219.4
5. Import (US\$ billions)	1206.7	14356.4	8398.8	5957.6
6. Change in GDP (%)	5.8	4.9	2.7	7.9
7. Change in GDP per capita (%)	3.7	3.7	2.0	6.5
8. Inflation (%)	7.4	3.9	2.2	6.3

Source: Annual Economic Report on The OIC Countries, 2008. Statistical, Economic and Social Research Training Centre for Islamic Countries (SESRIC).

A country's economic output is measured by its gross domestic product, GDP. The OIC total output in 2007 was US\$3692.6 billion, equivalent to only 6.8% of the world's GDP. It is also lower than that of the developed and developing countries (equivalent to 9.4% and 24.3% respectively). The top 10 OIC producing countries are Turkey, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Iran, United Arab Emirates, Malaysia, Nigeria, Pakistan, Algeria and Egypt. Together they account for 58 percent of group population but producing more than 73 percent of the group output [15]. The top producer is Turkey with US\$663.4 billion (18.0 percent of the group total) while the least contributor is Guinea-Bissau with US\$0.3 billion. The average growth rate of the group for the year was 5.8%, higher than recorded by the world and the developed countries but lower than that exhibited by the developing countries.

The richness of a nation is normally linked to its GDP per capita. The average GDP per capita for OIC countries in 2007 was US\$2595 (at current prices) which was 5.7% lower than that of developing countries (at US\$2752) and 68.9% lower than the world average of US\$8355. Its growth rate of 3.7% per annum was similar to the rest of the world, higher than the group of developed countries but lower than the group of developing countries. Azerbaijan reported the highest growth of 22.4% while Comoros experienced the lowest growth rate of -3.0% [15]. However, the richest OIC nation, Qatar with GDP per capita of US\$72849, exceeding the developed countries average, reported a growth rate of 2.9% which is lower than the group average. The poorest

OIC country was Guinea-Bissau with GDP per capita of US\$206 (less than US\$1 per day) and decreasing at a rate of 0.4% per year [15]. In fact, [5] ranks Qatar as the world's second richest nation in terms of GDP per capita while Guinea-Bissau is ranked 223rd from the group of 227 countries selected.

Another macroeconomic component is foreign trade. The merchandise exports of the OIC countries in 2007 amounted to US\$1356,5 billion which accounted for only 9.8% of the world total merchandise exports but more than one-fifth of the total exports of the developing countries. A similar pattern is observed for the import performance. The total merchandise imports of the OIC countries in 2007 accounted for 8.4% (or US\$1206.7 billion) of the world total merchandise imports and a modest 20.3% of the developing countries. The top ten exporting (importing) OIC countries accounted for 74.6% (70.3%) of the total merchandise exports (imports) of OIC countries. The top ten OIC exporting countries are Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, United Arab Emirates, Indonesia, Turkey, Iran, Nigeria, Algeria, Kuwait and Libya while the top ten OIC importing countries are Turkey, Malaysia, United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Iran, Egypt, Pakistan, Nigeria and Kazakhstan. On comparing the trade balance (the difference between the total merchandise exports and imports) the developing countries performed relatively better than the OIC countries, while the group of developed countries and the world experienced trade deficit during the year under consideration. Despite having the highest GDP per capita, Qatar is not listed as one of the top ten producing, exporting or importing countries.

Inflation is one of the indicators of macroeconomic stability. A low inflation rate is associated with a stable economy. The average inflation rate for OIC countries as a group in 2007 was considered higher than the world average and the averages associated with the groups of developed and developing countries. However, some OIC countries recorded negative inflation rate, particularly Chad (at -8.8%) and Burkina Faso (at -0.2%). The highest recorded was 22.9% by Guinea. Despite being rich, Qatar and United Arab Emirates also recorded a relatively high inflation rate of 13.8% and 11.0% in 2007.

As with most economies, the major economic activities of the OIC countries are services, industry and agriculture. The service sector dominates and provides the most important source of income in many

OIC countries, accounting on average 49.7% of the total GDP for the period 2002-2007 [15]. The share varies from 25.2% in Nigeria to 87.2% in Djibouti. The next major activity in the OIC countries is industry with a contribution of 38.4% average share in GDP. The share varies from 3.2% in Somalia to 69.1% in Brunei. The average share of industry in GDP exceeded 40% in 14 of OIC countries during the period 2002-2007. A clearer picture of industrialization is reflected by the performance of the manufacturing sector which contributed on average 15.2% of the GDP. However, manufacturing in member countries such as Turkmenistan, Malaysia, Indonesia, Tajikistan, Turkey and Uzbekistan is gaining importance, contributing 20-35% of their GDP. The third economic activity, agriculture is widely assumed to play a major role in most developing countries. But in OIC countries, agriculture contributed on average 11.2% of the total GDP during the period 2002-2007. The agriculture sector dominates in only five countries, all of which are least-developed countries (LDCs). The highest share of 60.1% was recorded by Somalia while the lowest share of less than 1% was recorded by Qatar [15].

From the above overview we can see that OIC is a relatively complex inter-governmental organization when viewed as an economic entity. It includes one of the richest nations of the world as well as one of the poorest. More than 70.0% of the country production, exports and imports are dominated by the top ten members. However, none of these top ten members includes the richest nation.

3 The DEA Methodology

DEA is a well-known non-parametric linear programming based technique used for computing technical efficiency score for a set of decision making units, DMUs. Its mathematical formulation has been treated in [3]. We stated below the output oriented DEA model employed in the study.

Suppose there are S decision making units (DMUs) to be investigated, each utilizes m inputs to produce n outputs. Further, let DMU_k , ($1 \leq k \leq S$) uses a combination of m inputs, denoted by $X_k = \{X_{k1}, X_{k2}, \dots, X_{km}\}$ to produce n outputs, denoted by $Y_k = \{Y_{k1}, Y_{k2}, \dots, Y_{kn}\}$. The output oriented DEA for DMU_0 under the assumption of constant return to scale, CRS is given by

$$\text{maximize } \Omega_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{subject to } -X_{0i} + \sum_{k=1}^S X_{ki} \lambda_k \leq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (2)$$

$$-Y_{0j} \Omega_0 + \sum_{k=1}^S Y_{kj} \lambda_k \geq 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_k \geq 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, S, \quad (4)$$

DMU₀ is technically efficient if $\theta_0 = 1/\Omega_0 = 1$ and all the slacks are zero for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$ and $j=1,2,\dots,m$. For evaluation under the assumption of variable return to scale, VRS an additional convexity constraint is imposed on λ_k , such that

$$\sum_{k=1}^S \lambda_k = 1. \quad (5)$$

This results in the formation of a convex hull of intersecting planes which envelope the data points more tightly than the CRS conical hull and thus provides technical efficiency scores which are greater than or equal to those obtained under the assumption of CRS. The difference in the technical efficiency scores under the two assumptions of returns to scale is mainly attributable to scale inefficiency. The output-oriented model exhibits some special features:

- The technical efficiency score, $\theta_0 = 1/\Omega_0$, such that $1 \leq \Omega_0 < \infty$ since $0 \leq \theta_0 \leq 1$.
- Proportional improvement in outputs for inefficient DMUs is given by $\Omega_0 - 1$.
- The number of peers among efficient DMUs for an inefficient DMU under evaluation is not more than the number of constraints which corresponds to the total number of inputs and outputs. These peers can be identified from the non-zero λ_k values.

- Each constraint is associated with an input (or output). This provides ease of selecting combinations of input-output mix by enabling/disabling the relevant constraint(s).

The objective here is to seek maximum Ω_0 that increases Y_{0j} proportionally to $\Omega_0 Y_{0j}$, $\forall j$, while retaining the input level of DMU₀ no greater than X_{0i} , $\forall i$. Improvement or movement towards efficient frontier by inefficient DMUs can be identified by inspecting the system of equations (2) and (3). Define the slacks t_i^-, t_j^+ , $\forall i, j$ by

$$\sum_{k=1}^S X_{ki} \lambda_k + t_i^- = X_{0i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \sum_{k=1}^S Y_{kj} \lambda_k - t_j^+ = Y_{0j} \Omega_0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (7)$$

For an inefficient DMU₀, say, the projected output on the efficient frontier is as dictated by its peers (identified from $\lambda_k \neq 0, \forall k$) and given

by $\sum_{k=1}^S Y_{kj} \lambda_k$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. This can be achieved by proportional

improvements of $(\Omega_0 - 1)$ in all outputs plus additional amount (termed as slack movements) of t_j^+ in output Y_{0j} whenever $t_j^+ \neq 0$. On the input side, equation (6) suggests that the level of input X_{0i} , $\forall i$ can further be reduced by an amount of t_i^- whenever $t_i^- \neq 0$ to those dictated by the

peers, i.e. $\sum_{k=1}^S X_{ki} \lambda_k$. Thus, $(\Omega_0 - 1)Y_{0j} + t_j^+$ is a measure of *under-*

achievement of output Y_{0j} , $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, experienced by DMU₀, while t_i^- reflects the *over-utilization* of input X_{0i} , $\forall i$. The projected position on (and the movement to) the efficient frontier can be expressed as

$$X_{0i}^\wedge = \sum_{k=1}^S X_{ki} \lambda_k^* = X_{0i} - t_i^{-*}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and} \quad Y_{0j}^\wedge = \sum_{k=1}^S Y_{kj} \lambda_k^* = Y_{0j} \Omega_0^* + t_j^{+*}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (9)$$

where $(X_{0i}^{\wedge}, Y_{0j}^{\wedge}, \forall i, j)$ is the position of the composite virtual efficient DMU on the frontier, and $(\Omega_0^*, t_i^{-*}, t_j^{+*}, \lambda_k^*)$ is the optimal solution of (1)-(4) for the decision making unit under evaluation, DMU_0 .

In this study, we employed three versions of (1)-(4) under the assumption of VRS in assessing the macroeconomic performance of the selected 54 member countries of OIC.

Model 1. This corresponds to the actual version of (1)-(4) with suitable set of selected input and output indicators,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{maximize } \Omega_0 \\
 &\text{subject to} \\
 &-X_{0i} + \sum_{k=1}^S X_{ki} \lambda_k \leq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \\
 &-Y_{0j} \Omega_0 + \sum_{k=1}^S Y_{kj} \lambda_k \geq 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \\
 &\sum_{k=1}^S \lambda_k = 1. \\
 &\lambda_k \geq 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, S,
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Model 2. Following Lovell [10] and Lovell *et al.* [11], in the production of outputs each country uses only one input, its macroeconomic decision-making apparatus, a bureaucracy collectively referred to as *helmsman*. And each country uses exactly one helmsman. Thus $X_k = 1$, for all

$k = 1, 2, \dots, S$. The equivalent model is thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{maximize } \Omega_0 \\
 &\text{subject to} \\
 &-Y_{0j} \Omega_0 + \sum_{k=1}^S Y_{kj} \lambda_k \geq 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \\
 &\sum_{k=1}^S \lambda_k = 1 \\
 &\lambda_k \geq 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, S,
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

In this version, the input constraint $-X_{0i} + \sum_{k=1}^S X_{ki} \lambda_k \leq 0$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$

, n , becomes $-X_0 + \sum_{k=1}^S X_k \lambda_k \leq 0$, since $n = 1$, and reduces to

$$\sum_{k=1}^S \lambda_k \leq 1, \text{ which is redundant since under VRS, } \sum_{k=1}^S \lambda_k = 1 .$$

Model 3. Following the methodology adopted in [14] terms like “inputs” and “outputs” are largely generic. Performance of undesirable attributes (such as inflation) is considered inputs and performance of desirable attributes (such as economic growth) is considered outputs. Thus, the input and output variables in model 3 represent undesirable and desirable attributes respectively.

4 Selection of DMUs and indicators

We apply the three versions of the model discussed above to the OIC member countries for the year 2007. We choose the year 2007 since it is the latest year where all the data are available. The macroeconomic performance of a country can be measured by the growth rate of its GDP, the level of employment, the movement of consumer price index (CPI) and its trade balance, amongst others. The government can use fiscal and monetary policies to achieve these macroeconomic objectives. Fiscal policy involves the use of government spending, taxation and borrowing to influence both the pattern of economic activity and also the level and growth of aggregate demand, output and employment. Monetary policy, on the other hand involves the use of interest rates to control the level and rate of growth of aggregate demand in the economy. However, data availability is a problem. Thus, for the purpose of our study one input and four output indicators are chosen to characterize and reflect the macroeconomic structure of the 54 OIC member countries. These indicators are defined as follows,

- Input (X): Total government consumption expenditure as a percentage of GDP which in some studies acts as control instrument. We employ this input indicator only for the multiplier model 1.
- Output 1 ($Y1$): The annual rate of growth of GDP, expressed in percentage.

- Output 2 (Y2): The ratio of merchandise exported to merchandise imported as a proxy for balance of trade.
- Output 3 (Y3): The rate of inflation as indicated by the rate of change of the CPI.
- Output 4 (Y4): The total labour participation rate (measured as percentage of total population ages 15 – 64 years) which refers to *the total population ages 15 – 64 years old that is economically active and supplying labour for the production of goods and services during a specified period* [15]. This indicator is chosen due to incomplete availability of data on the rate of employment.

The selected macroeconomic indicators for the year 2007 are depicted in Table 3 together with their data summary statistics. The main source of reference is the SESRIC database at <http://www.sesric.org/databases-index.php>. Except for the balance of trade, all other indicators exhibit relatively high standard deviations, especially the labour participation rate. The percentage of GDP allocated to government final consumption expenditure varies from a low 4.52% (Lebanon) to a high 30.61% (Chad) with an average of 14.72%. Twenty-five nations (about 43.9%) record final consumption expenditure above average. Except Azerbaijan, all OIC-FEC's final consumption expenditures exceeded 10% of their incomes (the highest being Brunei at 25.57% as compared to Azerbaijan's 6.53%).

Table 3 Selected macroeconomic statistics, OIC member countries, 2007

DMU	Country	X1	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
DMU01	Afghanistan	10.12	12.43	0.37	13.03	59.6
DMU02	Albania	12.36	6.01	0.51	2.94	60.3
DMU03	Algeria	23.39	4.60	1.94	3.56	57.3
DMU04	Azerbaijan	6.53	23.40	2.39	16.60	65.2
DMU05	Bahrain	18.24	6.64	1.42	3.39	63.7
DMU06	Bangladesh	5.11	5.61	0.76	9.11	71.2
DMU07	Benin	9.45	4.22	0.74	1.26	72.1
DMU08	Brunei	25.57	0.38	2.50	0.30	66.8
DMU09	Burkina Faso	18.69	4.23	0.48	-0.25	83.3
DMU10	Cameroon	12.09	3.30	0.96	0.91	63.8
DMU11	Chad	30.61	0.65	2.05	-8.81	74.1
DMU12	Comoros	12.24	-1.11	0.32	4.49	73.1
DMU13	Cote d'Ivoire	22.57	1.64	1.08	1.91	62.5
DMU14	Djibouti	26.21	5.21	0.74	4.97	67.3
DMU15	Egypt	8.17	7.13	0.83	10.95	47.3
DMU16	Gabon	17.58	5.56	1.94	5.03	70.9
DMU17	Gambia	8.53	7.08	0.66	5.37	76.9
DMU18	Guinea	5.40	1.51	0.74	22.86	84.1
DMU19	Guinea-Bissau	17.00	2.52	0.73	4.62	71.4
DMU20	Guyana	18.67	5.35	0.80	12.20	65.6
DMU21	Indonesia	6.68	6.32	1.16	6.17	67.7
DMU22	Iran	10.34	5.84	1.21	18.40	53.3
DMU23	Iraq	14.81	2.77	1.49	n.a	41.8
DMU24	Jordan	15.10	5.80	0.62	5.39	44.4
DMU25	Kazakhstan	7.12	8.69	1.16	10.77	69.4
DMU26	Kuwait	12.29	4.58	2.06	5.47	66.9
DMU27	Kyrgyzstan	12.10	8.28	0.50	10.20	63.8
DMU28	Lebanon	4.52	4.01	0.50	4.06	50.1
DMU29	Libya	13.10	6.80	3.39	6.20	52.7
DMU30	Malaysia	14.49	6.35	1.23	2.03	62.7
DMU31	Maldives	29.27	6.67	1.01	7.40	65.5
DMU32	Mali	19.11	2.48	0.81	2.50	50.1
DMU33	Mauritania	20.06	0.88	0.84	7.26	70.1
DMU34	Morocco	18.26	2.20	0.79	2.04	51.4
DMU35	Mozambique	13.68	7.00	0.64	8.16	82.9
DMU36	Niger	12.77	3.13	0.56	0.06	62.5
DMU37	Nigeria	26.06	6.40	2.06	5.47	54.5
DMU38	Oman	30.16	6.41	1.43	5.89	55.2
DMU39	Pakistan	12.70	6.40	0.66	7.77	53.8
DMU40	Palestine	16.11	0.00	0.17	n.a	40.8
DMU41	Qatar	19.50	14.23	1.89	13.76	77.2
DMU42	Saudi Arabia	26.36	4.14	1.65	4.11	54.3
DMU43	Senegal	10.38	5.03	0.63	5.87	73.3
DMU44	Sierra Leone	16.87	6.82	0.47	11.65	66.1

Table 3 (Continue)

DMU	Country	X1	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
DMU45	Somalia	9.96	2.68	0.18	n.a	71.1
DMU46	Sudan	13.72	10.52	0.81	7.98	51.5
DMU47	Suriname	4.67	5.53	0.87	6.43	51.1
DMU48	Syria	11.21	3.88	1.12	4.68	49.8
DMU49	Tajikistan	8.63	7.78	0.76	13.17	61.5
DMU50	Togo	10.53	2.07	0.58	0.96	68.9
DMU51	Tunisia	14.91	6.33	0.97	3.15	48.3
DMU52	Turkey	10.31	5.07	0.80	8.76	47.5
DMU53	Turkmenistan	13.36	11.61	1.16	6.26	64.8
DMU54	Uganda	9.26	6.49	0.33	6.80	85.9
DMU55	United Arab Emirates	10.55	7.67	1.39	11.13	77.7
DMU56	Uzbekistan	17.12	9.50	1.26	12.28	64.2
DMU57	Yemen	14.28	3.08	0.86	12.48	43.9
Data summary statistics	Mean :	14.72	5.59	1.05	6.65	62.7
	Standard deviation:	6.61	3.84	0.64	5.27	11.3
	Minimum :	4.52	-1.11	0.17	-8.81	40.8
	Maximum :	30.61	23.40	3.39	22.86	85.9

Notes:

X1: Final total government consumption expenditure (% of GDP)

Y1: Growth rate of real GDP (%)

Y2: Balance of trade (=Value of export/Value of import)

Y3: Rate of inflation (change in CPI, %)

Y4: Labour participation rate (ages 15 – 64 years, %).

Source: *Annual Economic Report on The OIC Countries, 2008*. Statistical Economic and Social Research Training Centre for Islamic Countries (SESERIC).

The highest economic growth is lead by Azerbaijan (23.40%) while Comoros recorded a negative growth of -1.11%. The average economic growth for OIC is 5.59% with a standard deviation of 3.84%. Only four countries recorded two-digit percentage growth rate. However, these four high-growth countries do not contribute to the ten OIC high-producing countries which accounted for 73% of the total OIC output in 2007 [15]. As a group, OIC countries recorded a small trade balance surplus in 2007. Five members of OIC-FEC exhibited a significant trade balance (of more than 2.0). These are Azerbaijan, Brunei, Kuwait, Libya and Nigeria. Libya recorded the highest trade balance of 3.39 while Palestine recorded the lowest at 0.17, followed by Somalia (0.18),

Uganda (0.33) and Afghanistan (0.37). These poor trade performers are also considered as politically unstable entities.

The average rate of inflation for the OIC countries in 2007 was about 6.65% which was considerably higher than the world's average of 3.90% and the average recorded by the developed and developing countries (2.20% and 6.30% respectively). The worst hit was Guinea (22.86%), followed by Qatar (13.76%), Tajikistan (13.17%) and Afghanistan (13.03%) while two OIC-LDC, Burkina Faso and Chad recorded a negative rate of -0.25% and -8.81% respectively. No data was available for three countries (Iraq, Palestine and Somalia). In fact, in Somalia it was reported that businesses print their own money, so inflation rate cannot be easily determined ([http://www.indexmundi.com/somalia/inflation_rate\(consumer_price\).html](http://www.indexmundi.com/somalia/inflation_rate(consumer_price).html)) The last indicator is total labour participation rate (ages 15 – 64 years old). The highest is 85.9% as recorded by Uganda, followed by Guinea (84.1%), Burkina Faso (83.3%) and Mozambique (82.9%). These are OIC-LDC from Sub-Saharan Africa region. Eight nations recorded a labour participation rate of less than 50%, the two lowest being Palestine (40.8%) and Iraq (41.8%). However, as a group, on average 62.72% of the total population in age group 15 – 64 years is economically active and contributing to the labour market.

Due to the non-availability of data on the rate of inflation for Iraq, Palestine and Somalia, we focus our study on the remaining 54 member countries. The indicators of input, balance of trade and labour participation rate take a strictly positive value for all observations. The rate of economic growth and inflation indicators take on negative value for some observations, and DEA is not capable of handling negative values. Thus, for consistency all indicators were normalized on a scale of [1, 10] such that the followings hold [13].

- For indicators whose large positive values are desirable (Y_1 , Y_2 and Y_4), we adopt the transformation

$$X_{nor} = \frac{9(X_{act} - X_{min})}{X_{max} - X_{min}} + 1 \quad (12)$$

where X_{nor} is the value of the normalized indicator,
 X_{act} is the actual value of the indicator,

X_{max} is the maximum value of the indicator,

X_{min} is the minimum value of the indicator.

This transformation ensures that $X_{nor} \in [1, 10]$.

- For indicators whose small values are preferable (such as $Y3$), we adopt the transformation

$$X_{nor} = \frac{9(X_{max}-X_{act})}{X_{max}-X_{min}} + 1 \quad (13)$$

where X_{nor} is the value of the normalized indicator,

X_{act} is the actual value of the indicator,

X_{max} is the maximum value of the indicator,

X_{min} is the minimum value of the indicator.

This transformation ensures that $X_{nor} \in [1, 10]$.

5 DEA Results and Interpretations

We used linear programming software, LINDO to solve the DEA model under the assumption of VRS for the three models. This amounts to running the program 162 times. The relative technical efficiency scores (which act as performance indicators for each nation) are presented in Table 4. The results obtained are consistent for the three models with model 1 producing a relatively higher score, followed by model 2 and model 3. The mean absolute deviations, MAD between each model is less than 0.5% with an average score of 0.8864, 0.8288 and 0.7325 respectively. Model 1 suggested 14 nations were technically efficient in converting the input to outputs. However, in the absence of the input indicator, both model 2 and model 3 shortlisted seven nations as being technically efficient.

Table 4 Technical efficiency results for OIC member countries, 2007

DMU	Country	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	<i>TE_{average}</i>
DMU01	Afghanistan	0.8109	0.7822	0.7064	0.7665
DMU02	Albania	0.9571	0.8567	0.6808	0.8315
DMU03	Algeria	0.8084	0.8021	0.8021	0.8042
DMU04	Azerbaijan	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU05	Bahrain	0.8995	0.8616	0.7562	0.8391
DMU06	Bangladesh	1.0000	0.7923	0.7695	0.8539
DMU07	Benin	1.0000	0.8897	0.8145	0.9014
DMU08	Brunei	0.9966	0.9966	0.9966	0.9966
DMU09	Burkina Faso	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU10	Cameroon	0.9750	0.8327	0.6788	0.8288
DMU11	Chad	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU12	Comoros	0.8875	0.7993	0.7648	0.8172
DMU13	Cote d'Ivoire	0.7982	0.7596	0.5680	0.7086
DMU14	Djibouti	0.8109	0.8109	0.7192	0.7803
DMU15	Egypt	0.7711	0.6877	0.4904	0.6497
DMU16	Gabon	0.9715	0.9289	0.9286	0.9430
DMU17	Gambia	1.0000	0.9217	0.8641	0.9286
DMU18	Guinea	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU19	Guinea-Bissau	0.8224	0.7935	0.7760	0.7973
DMU20	Guyana	0.6920	0.6920	0.6661	0.6834
DMU21	Indonesia	1.0000	0.8173	0.7596	0.8589
DMU22	Iran	0.5654	0.5439	0.5430	0.5508
DMU23	Iraq
DMU24	Jordan	0.8482	0.7865	0.5512	0.7286
DMU25	Kazakhstan	0.9300	0.8179	0.7813	0.8431
DMU26	Kuwait	0.9993	0.9011	0.9006	0.9337
DMU27	Kyrgyzstan	0.7901	0.7603	0.6876	0.7460
DMU28	Lebanon	1.0000	0.7724	0.4852	0.7525
DMU29	Libya	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU30	Malaysia	0.9703	0.8876	0.7427	0.8669
DMU31	Maldives	0.7858	0.7859	0.7123	0.7613
DMU32	Mali	0.8293	0.7704	0.4297	0.6765
DMU33	Mauritania	0.7677	0.7677	0.7601	0.7652
DMU34	Morocco	0.8434	0.7736	0.4367	0.6845
DMU35	Mozambique	0.9769	0.9769	0.9763	0.9767
DMU36	Niger	0.9854	0.8508	0.6728	0.8363
DMU37	Nigeria	0.8458	0.8458	0.7490	0.8135
DMU38	Oman	0.7939	0.7939	0.6246	0.7374
DMU39	Pakistan	0.8134	0.7472	0.5366	0.6991
DMU40	Palestine
DMU41	Qatar	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU42	Saudi Arabia	0.7785	0.7785	0.6493	0.7354
DMU43	Senegal	0.9066	0.8413	0.8074	0.8517
DMU44	Sierra Leone	0.7253	0.7253	0.6846	0.7118

Table 4 (Continue)

DMU	Country	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	<i>TE_{average}</i>
DMU45	Somalia				
DMU46	Sudan	0.8920	0.8560	0.7333	0.8271
DMU47	Suriname	1.0000	0.7557	0.5125	0.7561
DMU48	Syria	0.8855	0.7552	0.5016	0.7141
DMU49	Tajikistan	0.7210	0.6822	0.6309	0.6780
DMU50	Togo	0.9911	0.8232	0.7188	0.8443
DMU51	Tunisia	0.9319	0.8595	0.6648	0.8187
DMU52	Turkey	0.7699	0.6833	0.4336	0.6289
DMU53	Turkmenistan	0.9741	0.9301	0.8664	0.9235
DMU54	Uganda	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
DMU55	United Arab Emirates	1.0000	0.9589	0.9578	0.9722
DMU56	Uzbekistan	0.7615	0.7615	0.7179	0.7470
DMU57	Yemen	0.5846	0.5372	0.3472	0.4897
	Mean :	0.8864	0.8288	0.7325	0.8159
	Minimum :	0.5654	0.5372	0.3472	0.4897

These seven nations comprised of three OIC-FEC and four OIC-LDC, each exhibiting superiority in one or more indicators or combinations of indicators. Azerbaijan (DMU04) recorded the highest rate of growth of GDP of 23.39% in 2007 (20.95% and 13.25% in 2006 and 2005 respectively) while maintaining a low level of total government consumption expenditure at 6.53% of GDP. It also experienced a favorable trade balance with export of merchandise and services more than double the import of merchandise and services. However, its rate of inflation of 16.6% was above the group's average of 6.65%. Libya (DMU29) is another top performer, mainly due to its superiority in balance of trade where the values of its exports more than triple the values of its imports. Its GDP growth rate of 6.8% was above the group's average of 5.59%. However, its labour participation rate of 52.7% was below the group's average of 62.72%. Qatar is another OIC-FEC performer shortlisted as relatively technically efficient despite exhibiting a relatively high rate of inflation (13.76%) and total government consumption expenditure (19.50%). These drawbacks were outweighed by the combination of the other three indicators – a high GDP growth rate of 14.2%, a favorable trade balance of 1.89 and an above average labour participation rate of 77.2%.

Four members of OIC-LDC (Burkina Faso, Chad, Guinea and Uganda) were jointly classified as top performers. Burkina Faso and Chad were the only two OIC member countries experiencing negative rate of inflation in 2007. Both also recorded relatively high labour participation rate. Guinea, however, recorded the highest rate of inflation of 22.86%. But, its score for the fourth indicator of 84.1% is second highest in the group, behind Uganda who lead the group with 85.9%. Three members of OIC-MDC (Indonesia, Lebanon and Suriname) were found to be technically efficient under Model 1 but not under Model 2 or Model 3. This is strongly attributable to their favorably low input values of 6.68%, 4.52% and 4.67% respectively, which were much lower than the group's average of 14.72%. Thus, it appears that superiority in one or more indicators can outweigh other shortcomings or nonperforming attributes when employing DEA methodology with no weight restriction.

Table 5 lists the weights associated with the indicators as given by the dual values of Model 2. Two countries, namely Azerbaijan and Qatar had the contributions from all four indicators; two countries, namely Guinea and Uganda had contributions from three contributors; two countries, namely Burkina Faso and Chad had contributions from two indicators while one country, namely Libya had contribution from one indicator only. The contributions of technical efficiency for Azerbaijan and Qatar came from the growth rates and the labour participation rate, amounting to more than 68.8%. A low normalized inflation rate only contributed 10.2% and 13.8% to the technical efficiency. Guinea and Uganda capitalized on labour participation rate giving it a contributing factor of 89.9% and 91.1% respectively. The normalized inflation rate only accounted for 0.3% and 3.3% to the technical efficiency scores respectively. The technical efficiency score for Burkina Faso came from two sources, a high normalized inflation rate (37.6%) and a relatively high labour participation rate (62.4%). No contribution was made by growth rate and balance of trade. Having the highest normalized inflation rate contributed 58.2% to Chad's technical efficiency score. The other 41.8% came from balance of trade. No contribution was made by growth rate and labour participation rate. Libya monopolized on the balance of trade, making it sole contributor to technical efficiency score. Thus, with the exception of Libya, all other efficient DMUs take account of rate of inflation but at a manageable level.

Table 5 Sources of efficiency

DMUs	Weights	Normalized indicators	Actual contributions
DMU04 Azerbaijan	$\alpha_1 = 0.0436$	10.00	0.436
	$\alpha_2 = 0.0160$	7.20	0.115
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0385$	2.78	0.107
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0581$	5.87	0.342
			----- 1.000
DMU09 Burkina Faso	$\alpha_1 = 0.0000$	2.90	0.000
	$\alpha_2 = 0.0000$	1.86	0.000
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0496$	7.57	0.376
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0658$	9.48	0.624
			----- 1.000
DMU11 Chad	$\alpha_1 = 0.0000$	1.59	0.000
	$\alpha_2 = 0.0666$	6.27	0.418
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0582$	10.00	0.582
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0000$	7.65	0.000
			----- 1.000
DMU18 Guinea	$\alpha_1 = 0.0000$	1.92	0.000
	$\alpha_2 = 0.0382$	2.60	0.099
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0031$	1.00	0.003
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0932$	9.64	0.898
			----- 1.000
DMU29 Libya	$\alpha_1 = 0.0000$	3.88	0.000
	$\alpha_2 = 0.1000$	10.00	1.000
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0000$	5.73	0.000
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0000$	3.37	0.000
			----- 1.000
DMU41 Qatar	$\alpha_1 = 0.0436$	6.61	0.288
	$\alpha_2 = 0.0161$	5.81	0.094
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0385$	3.59	0.138
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0581$	8.26	0.480
			----- 1.000
DMU54 Uganda	$\alpha_1 = 0.0000$	3.77	0.000
	$\alpha_2 = 0.0390$	1.45	0.056
	$\alpha_3 = 0.0059$	5.56	0.033
	$\alpha_4 = 0.0911$	10.00	0.911
			----- 1.000

Next, we look at the relatively poor performers and try to identify the sources of their inefficiencies. Based on the average of the three efficiency scores, the bottom four were Egypt (0.6497), Turkey (0.6289), Iran (0.5508) and Yemen (0.4897). Despite achieving a reasonable growth rate, all four nations performed badly in two of the output indicators, Y3 and Y4. The rates of inflation recorded (10.95% for Egypt, 18.4% for Iran, 8.76% for Turkey and 12.48% for Yemen) exceeded the group's average of 6.65%, while the labour participation rate of 47.3%, 53.5%, 47.5% and 43.9% respectively, were among the lowest. With the exception of Iran, the other three countries also recorded unfavorable trade balance of less than unity. The main peers for these poor performers were DMU04 (Azerbaijan) and DMU11 (Chad) which exhibited superiority in Y1 and Y3 respectively.

For a more homogenous comparison, we omitted the twenty-one OIC-LDC, and used Model 2 to assess the remaining 33 countries belonging to the OIC-FEC and OIC-MDC subgroups. Results are presented in Table 6 which also includes the peers for the inefficient DMUs. The efficient DMUs are ranked according to the peer counts, the number of times a DMU appears as a peer for the inefficient DMUs, while the inefficient DMUs are ranked according to their efficiency scores.

Seven OIC-FEC and two OIC-MDC top the performance list, with DMU30 (Malaysia) ranked first due to its high peer counts of 15. This is followed by five OIC-FEC members (Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Brunei, Gabon and Qatar). Another OIC-MDC top performer is Cameroon which is ranked seventh, followed by Libya and United Arab Emirates. On average, the OIC-FEC group recorded a relatively higher technical efficiency score of 0.9053 than the OIC-MDC group (of 0.8795). Although the bottom performer is from OIC-FEC (Iran at 0.5452), the next twelve bottom performers are from OIC-MDC group.

5.1 Identifying the sources of inefficiency

In addition to providing the relative technical efficiency scores, DEA also identifies sources of inefficiency inherent in the inefficient DMUs and projects targets or levels to be adopted by these DMUs if they are to be on the efficient frontier. To illustrate the computation involved, we will consider two selected inefficient DMUs (DMU05 Bahrain and DMU51 Tunisia). Their respective results are given in Table 7.

DMUs with zero slacks

For these DMUs, their projected values are fully dictated by their peers and given by the systems of equations (8) and (9) with $t_i^- = 0$, $t_j^+ = 0$, $\forall i, j$. Thus, for DMU05 (Bahrain), for example, we have $\Omega_5^* = 1.00519$, giving

$$\begin{aligned} X_{51}^{\wedge} &= X_{51} = 1, \\ Y_{5j}^{\wedge} &= 1.00519Y_{5j} = Y_{5j} + 0.00519Y_{5j}, \quad j = 1, 2, 3, 4.. \end{aligned}$$

This means all outputs are to be proportionally increased by 0.519% in all directions. These incremental values are associated with the radial movements and are given under the fourth column in Table 7. The projected values are the sum of the original values and their respective radial movements. These are recorded under the seventh column and represent the position of an *efficient virtual composite DMU (of peers)* on the efficient frontier which benchmarks the position of the inefficient DMU.

Table 6 Technical efficiency scores of OIC-FEC and OIC-MDC countries, 2007

Rank	DMU	Country	TE	Peer DMUs	Group
1	DMU30	Malaysia	1.0000	[30]	MDC
2	DMU53	Turkmenistan	1.0000	[53]	FEC
3	DMU04	Azerbaijan	1.0000	[04]	FEC
3	DMU08	Brunei	1.0000	[08]	FEC
3	DMU16	Gabon	1.0000	[16]	FEC
6	DMU41	Qatar	1.0000	[41]	FEC
7	DMU10	Cameroon	1.0000	[10]	MDC
8	DMU29	Libya	1.0000	[29]	FEC
9	DMU55	United Arab	1.0000	[55]	FEC
10	DMU05	Emirates	0.9948	[04,08,30,53]	FEC
11	DMU51	Bahrain	0.9651	[30, 53]	MDC
12	DMU02	Tunisia	0.9643	[30, 53]	MDC
13	DMU21	Albania	0.9509	[16, 30, 53]	MDC
14	DMU34	Indonesia	0.9497	[08, 10]	MDC
15	DMU13	Morocco	0.9490	[08, 10]	MDC
16	DMU37	Cote d'Ivoire	0.9442	[04, 29, 30]	FEC
17	DMU26	Nigeria	0.9421	[04,08,16,53]	FEC
18	DMU03	Kuwait	0.9224	[10, 30]	FEC
19	DMU42	Algeria	0.9153	[08, 29, 30]	FEC
20	DMU38	Saudi Arabia	0.8998	[04, 29, 30]	FEC
21	DMU25	Oman	0.8982	[16, 41, 53]	MDC
22	DMU28	Kazakhstan	0.8965	[10, 30]	MDC
23	DMU24	Lebanon	0.8807	[30, 53]	MDC
24	DMU48	Jordan	0.8759	[08, 10, 30]	MDC
25	DMU27	Syria	0.8472	[16, 41, 53]	MDC
26	DMU47	Kyrgyzstan	0.8445	[30, 53]	MDC
27	DMU56	Suriname	0.8255	[04,16,41,53]	MDC
28	DMU39	Uzbekistan	0.8251	[30, 53]	MDC
29	DMU20	Pakistan	0.7845	[16, 41, 55]	MDC
30	DMU52	Guyana	0.7599	[30, 53]	MDC
31	DMU49	Turkey	0.7489	[16, 41, 55]	MDC
32	DMU15	Tajikistan	0.7437	[04, 30, 53]	MDC
33	DMU22	Egypt	0.5452	[04,08,29,41]	FEC
		Iran			

Average: 0.9053 (All), 0.9403 (OIC-FEC), 0.8794 (OIC-MDC)

Table 7 Results for selected inefficient DMUs (2007)

DMUs	Variable	Normalized value	Radial movement	Slack value	Normalized projected value	Projected value	Original value	Percentage change
DMU05 Bahrain $\Omega_5 = 1.00519$ $TE = 0.9948$	Y1	3.80	0.0197	0.00	3.8197	6.64	6.60	0.6
	Y2	4.76	0.0247	0.00	4.7847	1.43	1.42	0.7
	Y3	6.53	0.0339	0.00	6.5639	3.28	3.39	-3.4
	Y4	5.57	0.0289	0.00	5.5989	63.84	63.70	0.2
DMU51 Tunisia $\Omega_{51} = 1.03612$ $TE = 0.9651$	Y1	3.69	0.1333	0.00	3.8233	6.65	6.30	5.6
	Y2	3.23	0.1167	0.5818	3.9285	1.21	0.97	25
	Y3	6.60	0.2384	0.00	6.8384	2.32	3.15	-26
	Y4	2.50	0.0903	2.8083	5.3986	62.84	48.30	30

DMUs with non-zero slacks

Next, we turn to DMU51 (Tunisia). The result indicates the presence of a non-zero variable slack, $t_2^+ = 0.5818$ and $t_4^+ = 2.8083$ associated with outputs Y_2 and Y_4 respectively. The position on the frontier is achieved by a radial movement of 3.612% of all outputs, followed by additional axial movements of 0.5818 and 2.8083 for outputs Y_2 and Y_4 respectively. A movement in all outputs alone is not sufficient to project the DMU51 onto the efficient frontier. Additional slack movements for outputs Y_2 and Y_4 are required for the DMU51 to match their virtual composite DMUs on the frontier. We can represent the results of normalized indicators for DMU51 in terms of equations (8) and (9) as follows,

$$\begin{cases} X_{51(1)}^{\wedge} = X_{51(1)} - t_1^- = 1 - 0 = 1, \\ Y_{51(1)}^{\wedge} = 1.036121Y_{51(1)} - t_1^+ = (3.69 + 0.1333) + 0.00 = 3.8233, \\ Y_{51(2)}^{\wedge} = 1.036121Y_{51(2)} + t_2^+ = (3.23 + 0.1167) + 0.58177 = 3.9284, \\ Y_{51(3)}^{\wedge} = 1.036121Y_{51(3)} + t_3^+ = (6.60 + 0.2384) + 0.00 = 6.8384, \\ Y_{51(4)}^{\wedge} = 1.036121Y_{51(4)} + t_4^+ = (2.50 + 0.0903) + 2.80826 = 5.3986. \end{cases}$$

A similar analysis can be conducted for all other inefficient DMUs (nations) in order to identify their sources of inefficiencies and the position of the composite efficient unit they are compared with.

5.2 Policy implication

On average, the technical efficiency scores for the OIC countries for the year 2007 are relatively high, averaging 0.8159 for all fifty-four countries and 0.9053 for OIC-FEC-MDC countries. However, some policy measures with the aim of strengthening economic cooperation amongst member countries is needed.

Most of the non-fuel producer are agriculture based economies. As demand for food is likely to continue to increase more rapidly, policies that have the potential to improve supply over time are mostly needed. Poor agricultural technology is the main factor that hinders agricultural output. Availability of water is a vital factor in maintaining and

increasing agricultural production. Thus, policy measures to improve facilities and land utilization are critical. Policy measures to improve such infrastructure could generate a considerable expansion in supply over time. Therefore, more efforts should be exerted in order to improve the infrastructure in agricultural sector through more investments, both public and private, and to create a favorable environment for foreign investment, including from the fuel-exporting members, in agricultural sector.

The high share of industry in the total output of many OIC countries, particularly in the fuel-exporting countries, does not reflect the high level of industrialization in the countries, since the production of oil and gas are classified as industrial activity. The low share of manufacturing in total output of many OIC countries is a clear indicator of the low level of industrialization in the countries. Improving the manufacturing facilities in these countries is utmost importance. The diversification of their production base would enable them to increase the value-added and quality of their products, helping them become less dependent on manufacturing imports and thereby increasing their trade balance. In addition, investments in agro-industry are another policy action in addressing agricultural and industrial development and unemployment challenges.

Inflationary pressures are on the rise. It has the potential effect of distorting macroeconomic and financial stability in many countries, including the OIC members. Thus, a prudent monetary policy becomes necessary in order to control inflation in the medium term.

The continued internal conflicts in some member countries, particularly in Africa, have undoubtedly serious negative impact on all aspects of life. It has impeded any efforts towards furthering the potential for economic development. It is hoped that such a conflict will come to an end. It is the role of member countries to try and find a solution acceptable to all parties. Thus, actions by governments, NGOs and international organizations are required to implement appropriate policies or programs to support the economic development in the OIC member countries.

6 Conclusions

In this study we utilized the DEA methodology and illustrated its applicability in measuring, assessing and analyzing the macroeconomic performance of OIC member countries for the year 2007. The three versions of the output-oriented model produced consistent results. Three nations were not included in the sample due to the absence of data on rate of inflation. When assessing the 54 member countries, the top performers were dominated by member of sub-groups OIC-FEC and OIC-LDC, attributable mainly to the superiority in one or more indicators considered in the assessment. For an alternative homogenous assessment the sample was reduced to include only members of sub-groups OIC-FEC and OIC-MDC. Seven members of OIC-FEC and two members of OIC-MDC were classified as best performers with Malaysia heading the list.

The paper also highlights how DEA can be used to estimate and identify inefficiencies and their sources. For inefficient units, DEA also identifies the associated efficient virtual composite units on the frontier comprising of relevant group of peers of efficient units and the directions to these projected composite units. This information is important and can aid the policy-makers in allocating resources more efficiently and identifying directions for improvement.

The study is by no means complete. Due to limited space and time, many important aspects of DEA have not been addressed. A revised DEA model with additional explanatory variables capturing essential features of the country's economic, fiscal, monetary, social and environmental aspects might produce valuable information in identifying the variations and shortcomings inherent in the macroeconomic performance. Others include the multiplier or weight restrictions such as the imposition of assurance regions (AR), issues of congestion, the restriction of integer-value variables, general multiple criteria decision making such as GoDEA and integrated analytic hierarchy process (AHP), dynamic changes in efficiency over time involving technological change and frontier shift (a study in Malmquist's total factor productivity), and random variable data chance constrained programming for the formulation of probability-based stochastic DEA model. These topics are receiving significant attention in literatures and provide directions and avenues for future research.

References

Banker, R.D., Charnes, A. and Cooper, W.W. (1984), Some models for estimating technical and scale inefficiencies in data envelopment analysis, *Management Science*, **30**, 1078 – 1092.

Beasley, J. E. (1990), Comparing university departments, *OMEGA, The International Journal of Management Science*, **18**, 171 – 183.

Charnes, A., Cooper, W.W. and Rhodes, E. (1978), Measuring the efficiency of decision making units, *European Journal of Operational Research*, **2**, 429 – 444.

Charnes, A., Cooper, W.W. and Li, S. (1989), Using data envelopment analysis to estimate efficiency in the economic performance of Chinese cities, *Socio-Economic Planning Science*, **23**, 325 – 344.

Central Intelligence Agency (2010), *The World Factbook*. Accessed on 22 June 2010. <http://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/rankorder/2004rank.html>

Cooper, W.W., Seiford, L.M. and Tone, K. (1999), *Data envelopment analysis. A comprehensive text with models, applications, reference and DEA-Solver software*, Kluwer Academic Publishers.

Despotis, D.K. (2005), Measuring human development via data envelopment analysis. *OMEGA, The International Journal of Management Science*, **33**, 385 – 390.

Kao, C. and Hung, H. (2008), Efficiency analysis of university departments: An empirical study. *OMEGA, The International Journal of Management Science*, Vol. 36, 653 – 664.

Karkazis, J. and Thanassoulis, E. (1995), Assessing the effectiveness of regional development policies in Northern Greece using data envelopment analysis, *Socio-Economic Planning Science*, **32**, 123 – 137.

Lovell, C.A.K.. (1995), Measuring the macroeconomic performance of the Taiwanese Economy, *International Journal of Production Economics*, **39**, 165 – 178.

Lovell, C.A.K., Pastor, J.T. and Turner, J.A. (1995), Measuring macroeconomic performance in the OECD: A comparison of European and non-European Countries, *European Journal of Operational Research*, **87**, 507 – 518.

Martic, M. and Savic, G. (2001), An application of DEA for comparative analysis and ranking of regions in Serbia with regards to social-economic development. *European Journal of Operational Research*, **132**, 343 – 356.

Nordin Mohamad (2007), A linear programming formulation of macroeconomic performance: the case of Asia Pacific, *MATEMATIKA*, **23 (1)**, 29 – 40.

Ramanathan, R. (2006), Evaluating the comparative performance of countries of the Middle East and North Africa: A DEA application, *Socio-Economic Planning Science*, **40** , 156 – 167.

SESRIC (2008), *Annual Economic Report on The OIC Countries, 2008*, Statistical Economic and Social Research Training Centre for Islamic Countries (*SESRIC*).

Sueyoshi, S. (1992), Measuring the industrial performance of Chinese cities by data envelopment analysis, *Socio-Economic Planning Science*, **26**, 75 – 88.